

2 Poems by Adel Khozam

Worship

Winning a beautiful woman
equals half of life
and the other half
is to win a beautiful homeland

It does not matter whether you are
a polished businessman
or a tractor driver in barren fields
the sun will not distinguish between you
and in the eye of the cloud
both of you are fit to be swept away

In the eye of the wind
trees are green hats

Tomorrow arrives now
shakes hands with yesterday
and they part

I stand where I am
and my place is my time

I search for a woman
who becomes the homeland
not to worship her
but to deny her through love
for denial
is the religion of rebellious hearts

Betrayals

I know a woman
who carries her axe at night
searching for unfaithful men
but she finds no one

The drunkards never leave the bars
employees are servants of screens
politicians are in the swimming pool with the minister
and poets are mummified

in the solitude that precedes
the death of the poem

Betrayal once
was to look at your neighbor's wife

Today
betrayal is to hate yourself
to be cruel to others
and withdraw from them

to welcome death
and make peace with it
unconcerned with what is called hope
and not waiting
for the moment of your ascent
on the bus of days
that no longer moves

Bio

Adel Khozam is a poet from Dubai, UAE, and a member of the generation of modernists who pioneered the Arabic prose poem in the 1980s. He has published more than 22 books spanning poetry, philosophy, fiction, and literary studies, and his works have been translated into several languages. In 2020, he launched the *World Poetry Tree*, an anthology featuring 406 poets from around the globe, published as part of Expo Dubai's cultural program. He has received prestigious international honors, including Italy's Tulliola Poetry Award (2020) and the Medal for Best International Poet from China (2021).

In the Arab world, Adonis described his book *The Naked Spring* (2019) as the most significant poetic work in the first quarter of the 21st century. In 2024, he was awarded the Gold Medal from the World Writers Organization for his book *The Philosopher's Mail*. His most recent project, *Manseerah*, is a cosmic poetic epic created in collaboration with 86 poets from around the world, for which he received the Golden Medal from Great poetry movement in China.